

Partial Atrioventricular Canal Defect: An Educational Ultrasound Image

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1. Abstract

Atrioventricular canal defect results from an abnormal or inadequate fusion of the superior and inferior endocardial cushions. Both the complete and partial types of the defect are associated with the ostium primum defect in the lowermost portion of the atrial septum, left ventricular outflow narrowing and the atrioventricular valve abnormalities. The clinical diagnosis of partial atrioventricular canal defect can be confirmed by cardiac ultrasound. The aim of this paper is to present an educational ultrasound image of partial atrioventricular canal defect.

2. Keywords: Partial atrioventricular canal defect; Educational ultrasound image

3. Clinical Image

Atrioventricular septal defect which is also atrioventricular canal defect, common atrioventricular canal, and endocardial cushion defect [1]. It results from an abnormal or inadequate fusion of the superior and inferior endocardial cushions [2]. Both the complete and partial types of the defect are associated with the ostium primum defect in the lowermost portion of the atrial septum, left ventricular outflow narrowing and the atrioventricular valve abnormalities. Cardiac ultrasound helps in establishing the diagnosis of various types of endocardial cushion defects. Figure 1 shows an ultrasound image of an infant with partial

atrioventricular.

Figure 1: An ultrasound image of an infant with partial atrioventricular showing right ventricular hypertrophy, large inlet ventricular septal defect, and small ostium primum atria septal defect.

The atrioventricular canal is the "classic" congenital heart defect seen in patients with Down syndrome [3].

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In Down syndrome, complete atrioventricular canal is the prevalent defect, which is commonly associated with tetralogy of Fallot.

Partial atrioventricular canal and left-sided anomalies are more common in patients without Down syndrome.

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